

Thank you, Professor Karpenko! I learned a lot from you!

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Professor Karpenko — now *he* was a man, and a true Professor.
When I attended his lectures, it was the best lecture series of my life.
Maybe he was a bit like me?
I actually wanted to study history at first, and then... something changed.
Then I wanted to be a chemist — it was always halfway between the
two...
I remember how shyly I approached him, asking him to sign two books...
He barely said a word.
Just silence.
And I could feel his presence.
I wanted to be like him.

Once, I even had a fever — I took an ibuprofen just so I wouldn't miss the lecture!

In 2023, I visited the *Science Fair* as a guest and met one of his colleagues.

When I told him the story of my fever and the ibuprofen, we fondly remembered Professor Karpenko — and he gave me this book as a gift. It's still wrapped. :)

When you graded my project — I think it was on gold and silver — you didn't say anything. I just mumbled something...

Because of you, I pursued science.

A man who brought philosophy and science together...

